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**Initial Report on Algorithmic Changes and Memory
Optimisation for Heterogeneous Systems in
Plasma-PEPSC Codes**

WP5: Accelerated Plasma Simulations on Heterogeneous Systems

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Executive Summary

In this deliverable, we describe the initial efforts within work package 5 to port the four plasma codes onto GPU accelerators and heterogeneous memory systems. The presented strategies for each code are targeting the findings of the gap analysis performed in the beginning of the project. Progress has been made both on the individual GPU porting status of the codes, as well as in the exploration of architectural features of most recent GPU platforms and memory systems and according programming interfaces.

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1 Introduction

Upcoming exascale systems combine heterogeneous compute resources like CPUs, GPUs, and potentially other accelerators, alongside diverse memory architectures. Such systems offer important opportunities for large-scale plasma simulations, but pose a non-negligible challenge with regard to their efficient utilization. In this project, the four plasma codes shall be prepared for exascale-readiness. On one hand, this includes individual code-specific algorithmic adaptations. On the other hand, shared computation and communication patterns can be addressed with common optimization techniques in all the codes, enabling codes of different readiness-levels to benefit from each other's experience in the exploration of various acceleration techniques.

The objective of this work package in particular is to explore different accelerator architectures and techniques with regard to their potential to enable an efficient execution of realistic workloads in the plasma simulation domain on existing and upcoming exascale systems. In this report, the initial efforts in this exploration, including algorithmic changes, porting to and optimization for accelerators and heterogeneous systems will be presented based on the outcome of earlier gap analyses of the codes (D1.1-D1.4).

2 Background on Accelerators and Heterogeneous Memory

One of the main accelerators in use in current and upcoming High-Performance Computing (HPC) systems are Graphics Processing Units (GPU). Their specialized hardware architecture is designed with thousands of computational cores that can be utilized for parallel processing of multiple instructions on massive amounts of data simultaneously. Modern GPU architectures furthermore take advantage of the SIMT (Single Instruction, Multiple Threads) taxonomy, allowing a single instruction to be executed across multiple threads in a thread group - also called thread block. Some of the most prominent manufacturers of GPUs are Nvidia and AMD. While the exact setup of these vendors differs in terms of the grouping of cores and interfaces etc., both utilize similar computing concepts. For instance, most recent architectures of both vendors offer matrix engines, called Tensor Cores or Matrix Cores for Nvidia and AMD, respectively. These are specifically designed to accelerate matrix operations, and thus excel in machine learning, but also in high-performance computing applications.

In terms of the memory hierarchy, both vendors employ similar setups as well. Individual threads and groups of threads can utilize different memory tiers, including registers, shared memory, L1 and L2 cache, and finally global memory - ordered here from the fastest to the slowest tier. Registers are private to each thread, whereas shared memory is shared among a block. L1 cache can be specific to each thread or thread group and L2 cache is shared across groups. An efficient utilization of this on-chip hierarchy is critical to maximize GPU performance. Furthermore, modern GPU and other heterogeneous systems may utilize a heterogeneous memory setup in order to optimize data transfer rates and reduce latencies of the lower tiers within the memory hierarchy. Heterogeneous memory systems (HMS) refer to the employment of different types of memory technologies to optimize throughput, capacity and energy efficiency. Common today is for

example the combination of High-Bandwidth Memory (HBM) with Double Data Rate Memory (DDR), where the former offers a significantly wider memory bus and, thus, higher throughput, and the latter typically higher capacity. Further techniques for efficient data movement between the GPU and the system memory are for example the so-called GPUDirect storage, which enables moving data directly into or out of GPU memory, bypassing costly host communication. This is particularly beneficial for workloads that involve massive data processing and require frequent data transfers between the GPU and the CPU memory.

In order to best utilize the provided hardware features of GPU accelerators and heterogeneous memory systems, different programming interfaces are explored in the context of this work package. The most prominent ones are the following:

- *CUDA and HIP/ROCm*: CUDA and HIP/ROCm are the vendor specific programming interfaces for Nvidia and AMD GPUs, respectively. HIP can also be compiled for Nvidia hardware.
- *OpenMP*: OpenMP is a common interface for shared-memory parallelism, which only requires code annotations in the form of directives or "pragmas" and can be used both for CPU multi-processing and for GPU accelerator offloading.
- *OpenACC*: Similar to OpenMP, OpenACC is another directive-based approach for parallel programming more specifically designed for GPU accelerator offloading.
- *SYCL*: SYCL is another open standard that enables programming heterogeneous platforms using C++ without separating host and device code.
- *alpaka*: alpaka [1, 2] is a high-level C++ library for performance portable programming of heterogeneous compute architectures with a hierarchical parallelization model similar to CUDA. It supports backends for NVIDIA CUDA, AMD HIP/ROCm, SYCL, OpenMP, and oneTBB.
- *MPI*: MPI is the most established standard for distributed memory processing in high-performance computing. While it is not directly used for GPU programming, GPU-aware MPI enables the usage of MPI for clusters of GPU nodes by providing an interface to pass GPU buffers via MPI calls.

2.1 Example: EuroHPC Systems

LUMI is a pre-exascale EuroHPC supercomputer located in Kajaani, Finland. It is a Cray EX supercomputer supplied by Hewlett Packard Enterprise (HPE) and hosted by CSC – IT Center for Science. LUMI is capable of 375 petaflops of sustained performance and 550 petaflops of peak performance. The LUMI-C partition consists of 2048 CPU based Zen 3 compute nodes, each with two AMD EPYC 7763 processors with 64 cores each and memory capacities ranging from 256 to 1024 GiB. The majority of LUMI's computing power is provided by the LUMI-G partition, consisting of 2978 GPU nodes each housing four AMD MI250X GPUs, each with 128 GiB of memory, controlled by a single AMD EPYC Trento CPU (Figure 1). LUMI utilizes a dragonfly network topology

Figure 1: Architecture of one LUMI-G GPU node.

with the HPU Cray Slingshot-11 interconnect, featuring high performance RDMA and hardware acceleration for MPI and SHMEM based software.

Leonardo is a pre-exascale EuroHPC supercomputer currently built in the Bologna Technopole, Italy. It is supplied by ATOS, based on a BullSequana XH2000 supercomputer and hosted by CINECA. Leonardo contains 13824 Da Vinci GPUs, based on NVIDIA Ampere architecture, delivering 249,47 petaflops sustained performance and 323,40 petaflops peak performance.

MareNostrum 5 is a pre-exascale EuroHPC supercomputer to be located in Barcelona, Spain. The system is supplied by Bull SAS combining Bull Sequana XH3000 and Lenovo ThinkSystem architectures. MareNostrum 5 is hosted by Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC). MareNostrum 5 consists of several partitions: general purpose and accelerated partitions powered by Intel Sapphire Rapids CPUs, a next generation technology general purpose partition powered by Intel Emerald Rapids chips, and a next generation technology accelerated partition powered by Nvidia Grace chips. MareNostrum 5 is capable of providing 205 Petaflops sustained performance and 314 Petaflops peak performance.

The EuroHPC joint undertaking is further facilitated by five other supercomputers. VEGA, hosted at IZUM, provides 6,92 Petaflops of sustained performance with 2040 AMD EPYC CPUs and 240 Nvidia A100 GPUs. Meluxina, located in Bissen, Luxembourg, provides 12,81 Petaflops of sustained performance with AMD EPYC CPUs and Nvidia A100 GPUs. Karolina, located in Ostrava, Czechia, provides 9,59 Petaflops of sustained performance with 720 CPU nodes and 70 GPU nodes, each GPU node consisting of 8 Nvidia A100 cards. Discoverer, located in Sofia, Bulgaria, provides 4,51 Petaflops of sustained performance via 1128 nodes running AMD EPYC CPUs. Deucalion, located in Guimarães, Portugal, provides 7,22 Petaflops of sustained performance with a 1632-node ARM A64FX partition and a 500-node AMD EPYC CPU partition.

JUPITER will be the first EuroHPC exascale computer, to be located at the Forschungszentrum Jülich campus in Germany. The CPU partition will utilize the SiPearl

Rhea1 ARM HBM processor, and the Booster module will utilize Nvidia technology, both integrated into the BullSequana XH3000 platform.

As is evident from the list of current and future EuroHPC systems, enhancing the accelerator card support in Plasma-PEPSC codes is of utmost importance.

3 Porting Status and Optimisation Potential of the Codes

This section provides a short overview of the present state of the four plasma codes, focusing on performance critical kernels revealed during prior gap analysis and profiling efforts (D1.1-D1.4) and their potential code-specific algorithmic adaptations in preparation for the accelerator offloading. As all codes are either undergoing or have already undergone GPU porting, insights into the progress and challenges encountered will be discussed before diving into specific GPU acceleration and heterogeneous memory techniques. An overview over the GPU porting status, as well as the supported GPU platforms and programming interfaces is provided in Table 1. It can be seen that at this point all codes except from BIT1 already support or partially support GPU architectures from both Nvidia and AMD and that a range of different programming interfaces is used in the codes.

Code	GPU Porting Functionality	Supported Architectures	Programming Interfaces
BIT1	30%	Nvidia, AMD	OpenACC, OpenMP, CUDA, HIP/ROCm
GENE	80%	Nvidia, AMD	gtensor (Cuda, HIP, SYCL), OpenACC, OpenMP
GENE-X	70%		
PIConGPU	100%	Nvidia, AMD, Intel	via Alpaka (CUDA, HIP/ROCm, SYCL, OpenMP, oneTBB)
Vlasiator	80%	Nvidia, AMD	C++, CUDA, HIP

Table 1: GPU porting status of the four Plasma Codes.

3.1 BIT

Focusing on BIT1, a 1D3V Particle-in-Cell (PIC) code, it is specifically tailored for analyzing the distribution of power loads on tokamak divertors. The foundation of BIT1’s computational approach lies in the widely adopted PIC method used in plasma physics. This method involves tracing the trajectories of millions of particles within a field consistent with the density distribution, adhering to Poisson’s equations.

During the project’s inception, BIT1 initially utilized MPI on CPUs exclusively, lacking support for GPU accelerators [3]. As emphasized in deliverable D1.1, the results of the gap analysis highlighted the significance of the particle mover function, responsible

for calculating trajectories of millions of particles, as one of the most performance-critical aspects within the code. Consequently, in addition to the OpenMP and OpenACC multi-core CPUs (refer to D1.5), this deliverable signifies the initiation of efforts to port this computationally-intensive function to GPUs.

Looking ahead, a full port of the BIT1 code is planned for the future, employing further OpenMP offloading, HIP/ROCm, CUDA, and/or the Alpaka library. This endeavor necessitates transitioning the current code base from C to C++, an ongoing effort within the project.

3.2 GENE/GENE-X

Both, GENE and GENE-X are grid-based (Eulerian) gyrokinetic nonlinear codes which simulate plasma turbulence driven by microinstabilities in fusion devices. GENE uses a field-aligned coordinate system, which reduces the number of grid points and, therefore, the cost of the simulations, but can only be used in the core part of a fusion device. GENE-X overcomes this drawback by using the so-called "Fieldline coordinate independent" (FCI) approach, which increases the cost but makes it applicable to the whole device up to the wall.

GENE runs on all public HPC installations worldwide and effort has been taken to port the code to new architectures. Therefore, most of the code paths of this code are ported to GPUs already, but still optimization of some approaches has to be undertaken. GENE-X is a much younger code than GENE and the porting effort is ongoing. The GPU acceleration of GENE-X is mainly tested on NVIDIA GPUs. In the gap analysis of the deliverable D1.2 it was shown that a large speedup is necessary from using the available GPUs to reach the grand challenge of an ITER profile prediction. Compiling GENE-X on AMD GPUs was attempted but the Intel MKL library dependency of the field solver poses some portability issues. This issue is part of ongoing work of refactoring and optimizing the field solver of GENE-X.

First results of the porting effort with a directive based approach, employing OpenACC or OpenMP target directives, are shown in the deliverable D1.6.

3.3 PIConGPU

PIConGPU has been the first relativistic particle-in-cell code fully implemented on GPUs [4] and the first to be fully portable across heterogeneous architectures [5]. It has pioneered central data structures optimized for GPU acceleration such as super cells and particle attribute tiles [4, 6] as well as employing both data and task parallelization to hide memory copy times within heterogeneous memory hierarchies [4, 6].

Thanks to utilizing the Alpaka library for performance-portable heterogeneous computing, PIConGPU already runs on a variety of different compute architectures. As has been shown in D1.3 and D1.7, it fully supports AMD, NVIDIA and Intel GPUs, as utilized in LUMI and JUPITER in the future. A weak scaling of PIConGPU up to the full LUMI-G partition was demonstrated in August 2023 and can be found in D1.7. Additionally, PIConGPU already ran on x86, ARM and RISC-V CPUs, as reported in D2.1 and D2.2, respectively. Thus PIConGPU is ready for all compute architectures foreseen within the EuroHPC JU.

On CPU platforms, we note a low utilization of SIMD (single instruction, multiple data) units. The root cause of this is the current implementation of the particle-in-cell algorithm and its heavy use of nested loops, which cannot be efficiently auto-vectorized by current compiler. In order to improve the performance, PIconGPU relies on further development of Alpaka and compiler improvements towards enhanced SIMD support.

3.4 Vlasiator

As established in Deliverable D1.4, Vlasiator envisages a performance gap of factor $G \approx 51.53$. Identified current bottlenecks are MPI communication in general, and performance of the field solver. The action plan currently being implemented, which consists of porting all Vlasov operations to parallel GPU kernels (as part of WP5), will impact the two identified performance gap contributors by facilitating moving to a smaller number of nodes and MPI tasks, reducing the overall communication overhead for both the Vlasov and the field solvers. The secondary porting task of WP5 for Vlasiator is porting the field solver to GPUs as well, and will include efforts to restructure the data layout in order to minimize MPI overhead, potentially by solving the fields only on a subset of all available MPI tasks, and re-parametrizing the MPI decomposition in order to facilitate better MPI ghost communication via messages consisting of singular contiguous buffers only.

Porting of Vlasiator was performed by declaring the major data structures in unified memory, allowing efficient migration between CPU and GPU memory and ensuring the data remains always correct. Vlasov solvers and data reduction actions were ported one-by-one, verifying the correctness of the simulation at regular intervals and correcting possible errors before they propagate further. Vlasiator has been compiled, ran, and profiled on both Nvidia and AMD hardware, utilizing the CUDA and HIP APIs respectively, through the unified codebase approach.

Memory buffers are re-used whenever possible in order to reduce overhead in unified memory allocations. As of the writing of this deliverable, all major operations of the Vlasov solvers and associated metadata operations have been migrated to GPUs and unified memory. Initialization of the simulation domain still takes place on the CPU, but data migration patterns during initialization have been optimized. The field solver porting to GPU solvers using the lambda looping interface has been completed but has not yet been optimized to perform efficiently. The main Vlasov solvers perform relatively well, but metadata operations due to the sparse velocity space implementation of Vlasiator hinders performance. Another cause of slowdowns is unified memory page faulting between GPU and CPU memory when accessing small metadata counters. A likely solution is to move towards using unified memory only for large buffers of data and maintaining separate host and device counters for buffer sizes, manually ensuring their correctness.

4 GPU Acceleration Strategies

In the following, details of the programming interfaces, including a brief overview over multi-GPU interfaces, will be provided, followed by selected GPU acceleration techniques used or planned in the plasma codes.

4.1 Programming Interfaces

As most of the codes are originally build for CPU-based acceleration, accelerator off-loading to GPUs is performed using a range of specialized programming interfaces and libraries as introduced in Section 2.

The least invasive method is pragma-based off-loading with OpenMP or OpenACC, for example. This approach is used in GENE-X and explored for BIT1. GENE-X leverages the interoperability between Fortran and C++ for GPU acceleration in the following way: Compute kernels that are meant to be accelerated are ported to C++ and use OpenACC or OpenMP offload. The use of OpenMP offload is prioritized considering its portability across different GPU architectures from NVIDIA, AMD, and Intel. Other infrastructures that are needed by the compute kernels, i.e. mesh, are managed on GPU memory by OpenACC and OpenMP offload backend during the initialization stage which ensures minimal latency for switching between CPU and GPU computation.

For BIT1, the first efforts include a partial GPU port by off-loading the most computationally intensive kernel onto GPUs using OpenACC. The off-loading with OpenACC is achieved by annotating the code with OpenACC directives to copy data between the host CPU and the GPU and to distribute the main processing loop to the GPU work items using according pragmas. The same approach has been used with OpenMP.

The GPU vendor specific standards CUDA and HIP require rewriting the code following specific GPU programming paradigms. While this is a more invasive approach, it can offer more control over the performance. This approach is mainly followed by Vlasiator. Vlasiator is built with a unified codebase, which allows compilation of GPU- or CPU-specific modules based on compile-time arguments, with the majority of the codebase re-used between the two approaches. Support for both CUDA and HIP ecosystems is achieved via preprocessor substitution of GPU abstraction macros with suitable API calls. This approach relies on CUDA and HIP providing one-to-one matching calls and functionalities. Special consideration must be taken when utilizing calls which have near-but-not-perfect matching, such as for kernel ballot operations. For sections of the code which perform trivially parallelizable loop operations, an architecture-agnostic redirection layer has been implemented, which passes lambda-constructed loop operations to the relevant parallelism API (CUDA, HIP, or OpenMP).

In order to enable portability, existing libraries can be used to abstract away from the underlying off-loading strategies. For example, GENE uses a C++ template library `gtensor` as a midlayer and has abstracted all calls to any kind of accelerator to calls to this library. `gtensor` then provides backends for CUDA, HIP and SYCL to target the GPUs of NVIDIA, AMD and Intel, respectively. The approach has been described in detail in [7].

Another library with a broader, more diverse scope as `gtensor` is `alpaka` [1, 5]. It offers an abstraction in the form of kernels that are executed on a multidimensional grid of work items similar to CUDA or HIP, but supports a wide range of GPU-like and CPU-like compute devices, relying on advanced C++ concepts such as template metaprogramming, compile-time polymorphism and C++ concepts to replace `alpaka` code by the parallelization backend selected. Current `alpaka` backends are CUDA, HIP/ROCm, SYCL, OpenMP, and oneTBB. `Alpaka` implements a redundant parallel hierarchy similar to CUDA, see Fig. 2, that can be mapped to a specific hierarchy using the backends.

Figure 2: The alpaka redundant parallel hierarchy model and two possible mappings to GPU and many-core CPU architectures. As can be clearly seen the alpaka hierarchy lends its concept from CUDA.

Alpaka is broadly used beyond the plasma simulation community, accelerating particle tracking for the CERN CMS detector or digital twins of aeroplanes as developed by DLR. Alpaka routinely achieves close to native performance [2, 9], see Fig. 3, which compares the throughput of BabelStream [8], an implementation of the stream benchmark that supports different programming models, for various parallel programming models in comparison to a native CUDA/HIP implementation on LUMI-G.

Within Plasma-PEPSC porting of BIT1 and Vlasiator to alpaka is investigated. Since PIconGPU utilizes alpaka, there is only a single code base for PIconGPU independent of hardware specific preprocessor directives. In PIconGPU, algorithms are implemented as alpaka kernels, providing a vendor-free formulation of the code. During compilation of PIconGPU, the alpaka target backend for the chosen compute device is selected which maps the alpaka kernel abstraction to the corresponding vendor API.

4.1.1 Multi-GPU Communication Interfaces

While the programming interfaces described above can be used to offload compute kernels onto a single GPU, it is crucial for the exascale-readiness of the codes to support multi-node execution on an HPC GPU cluster. This can be achieved through interfaces such as GPU-aware MPI.

GENE makes use of a GPU-aware MPI library if available and a small performance increase can be observed in this case if also using GPUDirect RDMA capabilities implicitly via the MPI library. Similar to GENE, GENE-X also utilizes CUDA-aware OpenMPI library but the use is still very limited in the current stage. We have only confirmed this functionality on NVIDIA GPUs. Currently there are some compatibility issues between Fortran and C++ compilers which makes it an ongoing task to implement it in a portable and performant way.

Vlasiator, utilizing unified memory for particle distribution function contents, is capable of operating both with and without GPU-aware MPI but will benefit from lack of data migration in GPU-aware MPI environments. MPI simulations with multiple ranks have been successfully performed on both Nvidia/CUDA and AMD/HIP node architectures. Multi-node performance has not yet been tackled.

Figure 3: Throughput for BabelStream [8] implemented in a variety of parallel programming models, measured on LUMI-G. The CUDA/HIP implementation is the native reference implementation. Alpaka shows on-par throughput compared to CUDA/HIP, sometimes outperforming the native implementation as the alpaka code allows for better compiler optimization.

PICongPU makes use of a GPU-aware MPI library if available and a 6% speedup has been observed on Summit at OLCF. GPU-aware MPI can be optionally activated via the runtime parameter ‘-mpiDirect’ to the PICongPU binary call. GPU-aware MPI is routinely used on GPU-based HPC systems. On non-offloading devices, such as CPUs, the runtime option ‘-mpiDirect’ can still be used to reduce the communication latency and avoid serialization of data for communication.

For BIT1, multi-GPU execution is not reached yet, but planned for the future using GPU-aware MPI as well.

4.2 Performance Optimisation Strategies

Ideally utilizing the computational resources of GPUs for acceleration typically requires optimizations to be applied to the code targeting the data layout and communication patterns. As GPU-local memory is fast but limited in size, a common technique for off-loading large-scale simulations onto GPUs is blocking. This means that the workload is split into smaller blocks. These blocks are then mapped onto the work items of the GPU, enabling a parallel processing of a batch of data. Ideally, the block sizes should be chosen to fill the computational resources of the GPU completely in order to achieve a high occupancy.

GENE and GENE-X both have to recompute the right-hand side (rhs) of the Vlasov equation in each Runge-Kutta step (usually 4 per timestep) and solve the field equations. To fully exploit the GPU floating point performance it is necessary to use as large blocks

for these computations as possible. On the other hand is the memory on the GPU limited and exceeding the GPU memory leads either to crashes or to a very slow paging of memory. For the CPU code a blocking of the rhs computation has been used successfully for a long time. There the optimization for cache usage is the most important factor. On the GPU we usually try to use the whole rhs vector at once but are going to implement a blocking for smaller blocks if the full vector does not fit in the GPU memory. More details are provided in deliverable D1.6.

For Vlasiator, the main optimization targets currently are metadata and memory handling stemming from the adaptive sparse velocity space contained in each Vlasiator simulation spatial cell. Each simulation time step consists of six semi-Lagrangian advection operations, three of which are performed in velocity space, one for each Cartesian direction. Each of these three velocity space advectons can cause the distribution function to advect into regions of $f(\mathbf{v})$ which were previously not contained in the sparse representation, our out of regions which were previously included but no longer need to be. An algorithmic re-write of this velocity space adjustment was performed, but resulted in some parallelization corner cases and had to be reverted to a serial mode for some operations. Other parallelized actions currently depend on atomic memory operations, which have been found to cause slowdowns. Thus, there is a goal to perform twofold optimizations: metadata handling will be rewritten algorithmically to act completely parallel, and secondarily, these metadata operations will be migrated out of unified memory as much as possible in order to reduce slowdowns due to either page faulting or memory prefetch and stream synchronization operations.

For BIT1, in the context of optimization strategies, it becomes essential to explore the difference between OpenMP off-loading and OpenACC acceleration for a function in the code. This exploration is crucial for making informed decisions about parallelization methods, with the primary focus centered on porting the functionality of the most critical kernels onto GPUs. Simultaneously, two distinct memory management approaches have been explored. The initial exploration involved an explicit copy approach for memory transfer between the host and the device, revealing a significant impact of data movement within the particle mover function on overall performance. Subsequently, the second approach investigated was the utilization of unified memory, allowing the runtime to manage data placement and memory, potentially overlapping computation and communication. This approach proves advantageous when both the host and GPU need access to the same data during the simulation, a scenario more likely in a partial approach, as employed with both OpenACC and OpenMP off-loading. Comprehensive details on performance results are available in deliverable D1.5. Ongoing efforts in this deliverable entail further exploration of potential pragma-based performance optimizations for BIT1.

PIConGPU has initially been developed for many-core architectures making optimum usage of their hierarchical memory layers. Core principles of the design are:

- The grid of cells on each GPU is decomposed in fixed size tiles called supercells. These ensure constant GPU memory chunk sizes which are then mapped to an alpaka block abstraction. See Fig. 4.
- A fixed size chunk of particles is called a frame. Frames are stored in a double linked list. One double linked list exists per supercell. The fixed number of particles within a frame allows parallelization of threads within an alpaka block abstraction

Figure 4: PICongPU vectorized data formats for cell and particle data, super cell and attribute tile pool.

over particles.

- Use of thread-block exclusive shared memory where possible in order make use of its low latency and large bandwidth when accessing hot data within kernels.
- All data structure tile sizes (i. e. supercell sizes, particle frame sizes) and worker thread distribution block sizes (i. e. the number of threads per block) are set at compile time allowing better optimization by the compiler.
- PICongPU implements lockstep programming, its very own programming model, in order to reduce exposure of the user to the implementation details of the above techniques. See <https://picongpu.readthedocs.io/en/latest/prgpatterns/lockstep.html>.
- The combination of lockstep programming, fixed size data tiles, and fixed size worker block sizes are key to optimize accelerator occupancy. Higher occupancy typically results in a higher utilization of the compute device. For GPUs, occupancy is increased by keeping register footprint low, and keeping shared-memory usage per thread-block below a threshold which depends on the number of threads per block and the concrete GPU architecture.

4.2.1 GPU Matrix Processing Units

Modern GPUs from major vendors feature hardware-level matrix operation acceleration capabilities, referred to as Matrix Processing Units. Those units are specialized in performing matrix multiply-add, with tremendous floating-point performance. Those processing units are designed to perform the operation $D \leftarrow AB + C$, where A , B , C , D are limited-size matrices – typically 16×16 –, which contain floating-point or integer values. This feature was first introduced to accelerate deep learning applications, where

matrix operations are heavily relied on. However, growing interest have been observed to use this feature in scientific applications, such as physics simulations, as general matrix multiplication (GEMM) is one widely-used operation in scientific computing, that can be accelerated using Matrix Processing Units. In addition to those direct uses of matrix operations, which naturally map to Matrix Processing Units, the algorithms used in scientific codes can be adapted to run on those processing units; while such adaptation can appear counter-productive because of the need to adapt existing code and algorithm, the tremendous floating-point performances offered by Matrix Processing Units can justify it. We identified various opportunities to leverage Matrix Processing Units in plasma simulation codes, which we detail in this paragraph.

Matrix processing units have been implemented by GPU vendors under various names, and at different times. Nvidia was the first vendor to develop such processing units, under the name *Tensor Cores*, which were initially introduced in the Volta GPU architecture, and were incrementally improved over consecutive GPU architectures. AMD’s *Matrix Cores* have been introduced in AMD’s CDNA GPU architecture, and their capabilities have been improved with the release of the CDNA2 architecture. This second generation of Matrix Cores are available as part of the MI250X GPU, which power a large portion of top-tier supercomputers in the world, including EuroHPC’s LUMI supercomputer. Table 2 lists the floating-point performances of matrix processing units, for both Nvidia and AMD GPUs. We observe that the second generation Matrix Cores, available on MI250X, strongly outperform the third generation Nvidia Tensor Cores, on A100, for all datatypes, but most notably in double- and single-precision.

High-level, opportunistic use cases. The use of matrix operations in scientific codes is ubiquitous, under various forms. Among those forms, the general matrix multiplication operation (GEMM) is particularly relevant in the context of matrix processing units, as it is directly maps to matrix processing units’ multiply-add capabilities. However, the small-size requirements imposed when using Matrix Processing Units (typically matrices of size under 16×16) constitute an implementation challenge when looking for adaptation of scientific codes. Thankfully, vendor-provided libraries offer direct and transparent use of matrix processing units with minimal programming. Our evaluation showed that AMD’s implementation of BLAS – rocBLAS – implements a complex two-level tiling strategy to map arbitrary-size matrix operations onto the fixed-size Matrix Cores on AMDs GPU. This strategy is used in basic GEMM operations, and is automatically executed with no user intervention, for example in simple GEMM operations. Such strategy is the result of hardware-specific fine-tuning efforts, whose results are shipped

GPU	Processing Unit	Peak TFLOPS		
		double	single	mixed
Nvidia V100	1 st gen. Tensor Cores	N/A	N/A	125
AMD MI100	1 st gen. Matrix Cores	N/A	46.1	185
Nvidia A100	3 rd gen. Tensor Cores	19.5	19.5	312
AMD MI250X	2 nd gen. Matrix Cores	95.7	95.7	383

Table 2: Peak performance of Matrix Processing Units on both AMD and Nvidia GPUs, for the three levels of precision relevant in the context of scientific computing. “N/A” indicates that the given datatype is not supported

to the user as a ready-to-use library. We believe that this level of performance tuning for a generic use case, such as GEMM, is hard to reach with custom-made code, when using well-known techniques such as block matrix multiplication.

Low-level, algorithmic adaptations. While matrix-expressed operations are widely used in scientific computing and offer comfortable portability to matrix processing units, leveraging those units might not always be possible with existing algorithms. As such, low-level adaptation of part of the algorithms might be required to incorporate the use of matrix processing units in scientific applications. Through literature study, and experimentation, we identified sum reduction, and scan operations to be portable to matrix processing units [10, 11], as those operations can be expressed in terms of matrix operations, with well-chosen matrix values. The benefits of adapting an algorithm to leverage matrix processing units are heavily dependent on the type of application, and such benefit should be systematically evaluated on a case-by-case basis.

Both Nvidia and AMD provide libraries to perform matrix multiply-add operations on matrix processing units, by using collaboration of several (32 or 64) threads, under the names *CUDA WMMA*, and *rocWMMA*. Those libraries are low-level and reflect the actual architecture-level working of matrix processing units: the matrix sizes and datatypes are constrained by hardware-level capabilities. This approach is however limited by the reduced number of functions exposed by those libraries. For example, neither of those libraries allow direct memory access to matrix elements, which is a clear limitation, as modifying one element in one matrix could require a copy of the full matrix to shared memory, which is highly inefficient. On AMD, we are able to overcome this limitation, through the use of lower-level compiler intrinsics. Those intrinsics enable direct programming of Matrix Cores, and AMD-provided documentation details the hardware-level access procedure to matrix elements, from the programming language level. Such a programming interface is not available on Nvidia GPUs; to achieve the same purpose on Nvidia GPUs, developers must rely on assembly-level programming, and possibly, reverse engineering of existing libraries.

Precision for scientific computations. Matrix processing units were initially targeted towards deep learning applications, where lower-precision floating-point number representation can be used without significant detrimental effects on the training process. As such, the first generations of Nvidia’s Tensor Cores, only supported 16 bits half-precision values, with accumulation of consecutive matrix multiply-add results into a 32 bits single-precision matrix. Integer support is also offered across all generations. However, the growing interest for matrix processing units in the scientific computing community led to the introduction of 64 bits double-precision capabilities for matrix processing units, both in Nvidia’s Ampere architecture, and on AMD’s CDNA2 architecture. As such, matrix processing units can be used even when double-precision numbers representation is a requirement in a scientific code. As a side note, performance and energy-efficiency consideration can however justify the use of low-precision number representations for use in matrix processing units, since we observed that heavy computations on double-precision Matrix Cores on MI250X can significantly increase power use of the GPU.

The key insights of this study are:

- Efficient use of matrix processing units can be achieved with limited programming efforts through the use in scientific codes of high-level linear algebra libraries, such

as for example, rocBLAS.

- Low-level adaptation of existing scientific codes to make use of matrix processing units is a significant opportunity to improve performance. However, a thorough assessment of the impact on application performance must be systematically conducted when using such an approach, on a case-by-case basis.
- Low-precision number representation is no longer required when using matrix processing units on both AMD and Nvidia's hardware, which makes them particularly suitable for scientific application, which heavily rely on double-precision.

At this point in the project, none of the plasma codes are utilizing matrix engines. However, this study suggests that matrix engines are a crucial feature of current and upcoming HPC systems. Thus, above insights can be used to plan future usage of matrix engines for the four codes within work package 5.

A first attempt to utilize these has been performed for the PIConGPU code. The aim was to speedup parts of the in-situ radiation calculation. However, the required pre-computations to obtain the initial data in a format suitable to perform the radiation calculation in terms of matrix operations proved to be more complex than the successive computation by the matrix engines. This resulted in an overall decrease of performance. Thus PIConGPU stopped following this approach.

However, as these engines are an important focus of many emerging architectures, incremental improvements in their applicability for scientific codes and their computational throughput - as our study showed for the AMD MI250X - might make these features more attractive for the large scale plasma simulations of this project in the future. In order to evaluate the suitability for the other codes, an analysis of the potential necessity and applicability of re-formatting the calculations to be performed as matrix operations in all codes would be required. Existing libraries that might leverage the calculation transformations should be considered and potentially further studied before considering a direct application of the necessary transformations to the codes within this work package.

4.2.2 Mixed Precision on GPUs

Scientific codes widely rely on double precision number representation. This representation uses 64 bits to store and process floating-point numbers. In order to improve application performance, and reduce memory footprint, the use of reduced precision number representations is becoming a major topic of interest for scientific applications. However, as the level of precision is reduced, challenges need to be addressed to make proper use of this opportunity.

Double precision usually refers to the definition given by the IEEE 754 specification, which describes how floating-point number can be represented in binary format. Double precision refers to using 64 bits to store numbers. Single and half precision refer to storing floating-point numbers as 32 or 16 bits, respectively. Support for reduced precision has been incorporated in modern GPUs; Table 3 lists the peak floating-point performance for the three levels of precision on GPUs from both from AMD and Nvidia. The peak number of floating-point operations per second is significantly higher in half precision than both double and single precision, on all GPUs. As such, and combined with the

reduced memory movement needed for half and single precision, using reduced precision can theoretically provide a significant performance boost to scientific applications.

However, using reduced precision might not be suitable for all applications, as both the numerical precision, and the range of values that can be represented are reduced. This can have two notable effects on the results of a simulation. First, for iterative algorithms, where a convergence criteria must be met for the algorithm to finish, the use of lower precision may affect the speed of convergence, requiring more iteration for the simulation to execute. In this first case, the gain in floating-point performance might be counter-balanced by the increased number of iterations needed. In addition to this first aspect, the use of reduced precision might render the result of scientific application incorrect, and as such should be avoided. For those two reasons, careful consideration must be given to ensure that the use of reduced precision does not hinder the correctness of scientific codes. As this aspect is application-dependent, it needs to be evaluated on a case-by-case basis.

A hybrid approach regarding the use of reduced precision is called *mixed* precision, where two number representations are used in a single operation. This is for example implemented when performing a fused multiply-add operations $d \leftarrow ab + c$, where the factors a, b are represented using single precision, while c and d use half precision. This approach provides a higher level of performance than when using only single or double precision, while reducing the rounding errors induced by an operation performed fully in half precision, for instance when accumulating results of consecutive operations.

GPU	Peak TFLOPS		
	half	single	double
AMD MI250X	383	47.9	47.9
Nvidia A100	78	19.5	9.7
Nvidia V100	32.4	16.2	8.2

Table 3: Peak theoretical floating-point operation per second for various GPUs in half, single, and double precision.

For the two codes of the GENE family, we are investigating the usage of reduced and/or mixed precision for production runs. It has been observed that a switch from double to single precision usually does not affect the statistical properties of the turbulent phase. The question is, if we can go further and use some of the half-precision hardware features of modern GPUs or CPUs to speed up the simulation time. For this separate defined code parts are run in different precisions and the final results are observed to deduce a model for this kind of reduced precision runs.

Vlasiator has been built to utilize both double and single precision operations, with production runs usually performing operations on the particle distribution functions such as the Vlasov solvers in single precision, whereas operations evaluating fields or moments of the distribution functions are calculated in double precision. Support for half precision floating point numbers is not envisioned, as successful implementation of such a task would require re-normalization of all internal calculations, since Vlasiator currently performs all calculations in physical SI units instead of numerical units.

In PICongPU the user can specify usage of single or double precision for the simulation at compile time. However, in case the user selects single precision, a few computations

within the code remain in double precision, for example in the particle pusher, in order to ensure numerical stability. This makes PIconGPU an inherently mixed-precision code.

Notably, on AMD MI250X runs of PIconGPU in double precision are as fast as runs in single precision with regards to time to solution. Typically, double precision runs are slower than single precision runs since the compute throughput for single precision is twice as high, except for AMD MI250X where the throughput is equal.

An initial test of using half-precision in the current deposition algorithm yielded wrong results. Thus PIconGPU stopped following this approach. Lastly, for BIT1 mixed precision has not been considered yet, and its applicability would require further analysis that is not in the focus at this point of the project.

5 Heterogeneous Memory Approaches

This section covers heterogeneous memory approaches considering both heterogeneous hardware and according software interfaces to utilize the former. In this context, experimental explorations of available architectures and libraries have been performed to derive potential strategies for further optimisations of the plasma codes.

5.1 Heterogeneous Memory Systems

In current and upcoming HPC systems the most common heterogeneous memory setup is a mix of DDR memory on the host CPU and HBM memory on a GPU accelerator. First, we will look at approaches for efficiently utilizing the latter device memory, specifically in the context of a multi-GPU node comprising different memory regions and an interconnect between multiple chiplets. Afterwards, a DDR-HBM heterogeneous memory approach will be covered.

5.1.1 Device Memory and Interconnect Study

In order to understand characteristics of memory and interconnect on recent GPUs, we performed a microbenchmarking study of the most recent AMD MI250X GPU on a single node setup with 4 GPUs (as used in the LUMI supercomputer, Figure 1), each comprising two Graphics Compute Dies (GCD) that can be treated as separate GPUs. In the course of this study we explored data transfer options using different benchmarks to assess bandwidth, latency, and communication between the 8 GCDs. According to the specifications, the architecture comprises different sets of infinity fabric links between the different GCDs ranging between 50+50 GB/s bidirectional bandwidth to up to 200+200 GB/s for GCDs residing within the same GPU.

To evaluate performance and programmability of this setup we utilized the STREAM benchmark [12] for bandwidth, p2pBandwidthLatencyTest [13] for inter-GCD latency, and OSU microbenchmarks [14] for peer-to-peer and collective communication using MPI and RCCL. We utilized hipify-converted CUDA code versions for some benchmarks and RCCL-Test benchmarks [15] for RCCL evaluation. With the STREAM benchmark on the MI250X GPU approximately 70-80% of the theoretical bandwidth of the links between GCDs could be attained. The memory accesses over infinity fabric links across GCDs were made using unified memory by initializing the memory regions as "managed

memory” through according HIP API calls. When looking at access latencies between GCDs, the latency between directly linked GCDs is around $50 \mu\text{s}$. Other GCDs can only be reached over multiple hops, thus, resulting in higher latencies. Notably, each GCD exhibits varying latencies to other GCDs despite similar hop requirements. Furthermore, our ongoing study revealed that MPI peer-to-peer communication incurs slight bandwidth reduction compared to direct peer-to-peer memory accesses and collective communication with the RCCL library shows lower latencies than the same with MPI within a single node. Both direct memory accesses and MPI communication highlight the importance of GCD topology and distance on achievable overall bandwidth.

Data placement is an important factor in the given plasma simulation codes, both for load balancing and communication reduction, which has been revealed as a bottleneck in codes such as Vlasiator. The insights of this benchmarking study can help to develop memory optimization strategies within this work package that consider the importance of data placement to maximize available bandwidth. This will also require utilized load balancing libraries (such as Zoltan) to be able to utilize and act upon this placement information when determining the data-to-rank placement map.

5.1.2 HBM-DDR

Modern HPC hardwares, e.g., Rhea and Intel Sapphire Rapid tend to shift from homogeneous memories, mainly DDR, to heterogeneous memories combining HBM and DDR. To take the best of this shift, both the software stack and HPC application must be adapted. Exposition of fake heterogeneous memory information to the software stack is the preliminary step to prepare the shift. One way to simulate various memories is to use NUMA distance with dual socket machines. In this situation accessing local memory is faster than memory further away in the machine. The slowdown, due to latency between the two sockets on Ampere Altra machines, has been measured to 3.5 to 3.7. This ratio corresponds approximately to the bandwidth factor between HBM and DDR. Consequently, several tools have been tested and are in development at SiPearl for simulating the impact of DDR and HBM on CPU side.

5.1.3 GPUDirect Storage

Lastly, the feature of GPUDirect storage needs to be shortly discussed here, as it is a mechanism that enables a GPU to directly access remote memory without host CPU interaction. For codes which rely on checkpointing, such as Vlasiator, GPUDirect storage will need to be implemented in tandem with efforts of WP3, in order to ensure efficient storage of the full simulation state to disk. However, on stable HPC platforms checkpointing is expected to contribute only in a minor role to the total runtime, so implementation of GPUDirect storage has been declared a somewhat lower priority. For the other codes, such as GENE/GENE-X, there are no plans at the moment to make use of GPUDirect storage as diagnostic I/O is not a bottleneck from what we can see today.

5.2 Programming Interfaces for Data Management in HMS

The classical approach of data management between GPU accelerators and host CPUs consists of separate memory allocations on each of the two devices and explicit memory

copy instructions between those. Recent versions of CUDA and HIP offer "managed memory" API's, that enable accessing unified memory with shared pointers between host and device. As mentioned earlier, codes like Vlasiator are already utilizing this approach. However, further libraries specifically developed for heterogeneous memory management were explored in the context of this work package. Studying these libraries shall leverage the usage of heterogeneous memory systems in the future for all four plasma codes. All of the codes are highly dependent on memory and communication performance and specified libraries can facilitate an efficient usage of heterogeneous systems by improving data allocation, placement and transfers. Initial insights of the library studies will be presented in the following.

5.2.1 Concurrent memory allocation with mallocMC

The library mallocMC [16] provides an abstraction to mallocMC and is implemented in alpaka. It provides parallel memory allocation by a parallelized heap manager. The heap manager allocates a large memory space that is then managed by mallocMC. This way, application cases such as small object allocations on GPU architectures can be optimized. With the alpaka abstraction for memory allocation this allows to select the optimum allocation strategy for a broad variety of hardware platforms and application cases.

5.2.2 Optimum memory layout and reduced representations with Llama

Figure 5: The Llama data space provides a multi-dimensional index space as an abstract representation for data layouts. User-side data layouts can be mapped to layouts of the corresponding data in memory. Memory layouts can include reduced and compressed data representations. Support for both compile time and run time mappings exist. Memory layouts can be easily replaced by changing a single line of code. With Llama, memory layout aware deep copies between memory hierarchies can be realized.

The Llama (low level abstraction for memory access) library [17] provides a generic separation between user-side definitions of data structures and their layout in memory based on mappings, see Fig. 5. Although it breaks the C paradigm that the data layout on user side defines the layout in memory, it can be fully realized in C++.

Llama allows for easy switching between memory layouts via a single line of code, heat maps for memory access and reduced representations of data structures in memory. The latter feature allows e.g. for reduced precision storage of numerical values, lossless or lossy compression.

In heterogeneous systems, memory throughput depends on memory layouts optimized for concurrent access. Explicit copies between memory hierarchies can profit from knowledge of the memory layout. Compressed or reduced layouts can be used to increase parallelism by reducing the memory footprint of a single kernel and thus allowing for more kernels to utilize a local memory pool of given size. They are also useful for increasing data throughput and acceleration of floating point operations when using reduced precision representations.

5.2.3 H2M

OpenMP’s latest features like Allocators allow to allocate memory in various memory spaces through the `omp_alloc` function. Based on these features, H2M is a library that exploits these features by proposing an interface to allocate and migrate data between various memory spaces. Nonetheless, H2M approach is non-flexible since it relies on large modifications of the code source to integrate correct allocations and migrations. Alternatively, the SICM/Membrain approach proposes an online profiling of applications that helps to migrate data dynamically. This approach too has several drawbacks: slowdown of applications and modification of the kernel.

In this context, SiPearl started to work on an automatic approach, fully integrated into the LLVM compiler, that will be able to migrate automatically data. This approach is more flexible than the one proposed by H2M and less invasive than the one proposed by SICM/Membrain. The aim is to propose some new metric, to detect relevant memory for a given loop. With this metric, the hope is to be able to always have data in the fastest memory, when an access is required. This solution opens a variety of questions. Among them: the threshold where migrating data is more interesting than leaving data on “slow” memory, the migration of data that only fit partially in HBM, the migration of memory that is always coupled with another memory, the default memory for primary allocation, etc.

Additionally, the strategy proposed by SiPearl would help to define at least a tool that can provide useful information and metrics for data placement and migration.

5.2.4 StarPU

StarPU is a task programming library for hybrid architectures which facilitates heterogeneous computing. To explore data management in StarPU, we used SIMPIC, a PIC code extracted from OOPD1 [18]. Using this extracted PIC code to explore the possibilities of the StarPU library can yield valuable insights for further experiments with the large-scale plasma codes of this project.

Here we describe the implementation of a StarPU GPU task for the particle mover into the CPU version of SIMPIC. Task setup involves identifying arrays to be read/written by the CUDA kernel. In accordance with StarPU data management requirements, data arrays are assigned individual data handles in the global header file. Additionally, a structure containing parameters that remain constant throughout the code is initialized

in the global header. A codelet structure is defined specifying the associated function, the number of modified array buffers, and buffer access mode. StarPU vectors, representing 1D arrays, register data handles to corresponding main memory array pointers. Adjustments to the CUDA function focus on memory management without explicit host-to-device or vice versa copying. A CUDA-specific function was introduced in the GPU kernel for enhanced CUDA thread synchronization. Upon completion of computation, StarPU data handles must be deregistered.

StarPU code version runs show results identical to the GPU version of SIMPIC, supporting also multi-PU execution, e.g., with StarPU-CPU and StarPU-CUDA, for efficient computational resource utilization. Profiling of the StarPU code version shows that there are no explicit memory transfer calls. All the required memory transfers are transferred by the StarPU memory management and scheduler by itself.

With StarPU data can be partitioned into subparts for simultaneous use in various tasks. In the particle mover, particle arrays can be partitioned, enabling concurrent execution of independent calculations. The desired number of subparts is globally defined in the global header. This partitioning is implemented using StarPU-filter, specifying the data type (vector) and the number of partitions. Once partitioned, multiple tasks can be launched by StarPU, each independently operating on a distinct subpart.

6 Conclusion

In this deliverable, we provide an initial report on the GPU porting status and strategies of the four plasma codes. We show varying levels of porting progress in the different codes, with PIconGPU fully running on GPUs since the start of the project. The functional porting of GENE/GENE-X and Vlasiator is nearly complete and for BIT1 the most computationally intensive kernels have been ported. Next steps include fully migrating the functionality of the last three codes onto GPUs and subsequently focusing on potential performance improvements. To address the latter, this deliverable presented initial studies on recent GPU features such as matrix engines and unified memory, as well as an exploration of heterogeneous memory systems and libraries, that can be leveraged to guide the future optimizations of the codes.

References

- [1] Erik Zenker, Benjamin Worpitz, René Widera, Axel Huebl, Guido Juckeland, Andreas Knüpfer, Wolfgang E. Nagel, and Michael Bussmann. Alpaka - an abstraction library for parallel kernel acceleration. IEEE Computer Society, May 2016.
- [2] A. Matthes, R. Widera, E. Zenker, B. Worpitz, A. Huebl, and M. Bussmann. Tuning and optimization for a variety of many-core architectures without changing a single line of implementation code using the alpaka library. Jun 2017.
- [3] Jeremy J. Williams, David Tskhakaya, Stefan Costea, Ivy B. Peng, Marta Garcia-Gasulla, and Stefano Markidis. Leveraging hpc profiling & tracing tools to understand the performance of particle-in-cell monte carlo simulations. *Euro-Par 2023: Parallel Processing Workshops: Euro-Par 2023 International Workshops, Limassol, Cyprus, August 28–September 1. Limassol, Cyprus: Springer Nature, arXiv preprint arXiv:2306.16512*, 2023.
- [4] Heiko Burau, Renée Widera, Wolfgang Hönig, Guido Juckeland, Alexander Debus, Thomas Kluge, Ulrich Schramm, Tomas E. Cowan, Roland Sauerbrey, and Michael Bussmann. Picongpu: A fully relativistic particle-in-cell code for a gpu cluster. *IEEE Transactions on Plasma Science*, 38(10):2831–2839, 2010.
- [5] Benjamin Worpitz. Investigating performance portability of a highly scalable particle-in-cell simulation code on various multi-core architectures, Sep 2015.
- [6] M. Bussmann, H. Burau, T. E. Cowan, A. Debus, A. Huebl, G. Juckeland, T. Kluge, W. E. Nagel, R. Pausch, F. Schmitt, U. Schramm, J. Schuchart, and R. Widera. Radiative signatures of the relativistic kelvin-helmholtz instability. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on High Performance Computing, Networking, Storage and Analysis, SC '13*, New York, NY, USA, 2013. Association for Computing Machinery.
- [7] K. Germaschewski, B. Allen, T. Dannert, M. Hrywniak, J. Donaghy, G. Merlo, S. Ethier, E. D’Azevedo, F. Jenko, and A. Bhattacharjee. Toward exascale whole-device modeling of fusion devices: Porting the GENE gyrokinetic microturbulence code to GPU. *PHYSICS OF PLASMAS*, 28(6), JUN 2021.
- [8] Deakin T, Price J, Martineau M, and McIntosh-Smith S. valuating attainable memory bandwidth of parallel programming models via babelstream. *international journal of computational science and engineering*. 17(3), 2018.
- [9] George S. Markomanolis, Aksel Alpay, Jeffrey Young, Michael Klemm, Nicholas Malaya, Aniello Esposito, Jussi Heikonen, Sergei Bastrakov, Alexander Debus, Thomas Kluge, Klaus Steiniger, Jan Stephan, Rene Widera, and Michael Bussmann. Evaluating gpu programming models for the lumi supercomputer. In Dhabaleswar K. Panda and Michael Sullivan, editors, *Supercomputing Frontiers*, pages 79–101, Cham, 2022. Springer International Publishing.

- [10] Abdul Dakkak, Cheng Li, Jinjun Xiong, Isaac Gelado, and Wen-mei Hwu. Accelerating reduction and scan using tensor core units. In *Proceedings of the ACM International Conference on Supercomputing, ICS '19*, page 46–57, New York, NY, USA, 2019. Association for Computing Machinery.
- [11] Gabin Schieffer and Ivy Peng. Accelerating drug discovery in autodock-gpu with tensor cores. In José Cano, Marios D. Dikaiakos, George A. Papadopoulos, Miquel Pericàs, and Rizos Sakellariou, editors, *Euro-Par 2023: Parallel Processing*, pages 608–622, Cham, 2023. Springer Nature Switzerland.
- [12] Stream. <https://www.cs.virginia.edu/stream/>, 2023.
- [13] p2pbandwidthlatencytest. <https://github.com/NVIDIA/cuda-samples/>, 2023.
- [14] Osu mircobenchmarks. <https://mvapich.cse.ohio-state.edu/benchmarks/>, 2023.
- [15] Rccl tests. <https://github.com/ROCmSoftwarePlatform/rccl-tests>, 2023.
- [16] mallocmc. <https://github.com/alpaka-group/mallocMC>, 2023.
- [17] Bernhard Manfred Gruber, Guilherme Amadio, Jakob Blomer, Alexander Matthes, René Widera, and Michael Bussmann. Llama: The low-level abstraction for memory access. *Software: Practice and Experience*, 53(1):115–141, 2023.
- [18] J.P. Verboncoeur, M.V. Alves, V. Vahedi, and C.K. Birdsall. Simultaneous potential and circuit solution for 1d bounded plasma particle simulation codes. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 104(2):321–328, 1993.